

STUDY OF QUALITY OF GROUNDWATER OF VADODARA CITY

Sachin B. Shah

Student, M E (Civil) Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara – 390 001.

Email : sachin_umreth@rediffmail.com

Dr. Sanskriti S. Mujumdar

Associate Professor, Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara – 390 001.

Email: sanskritimujumdar@yahoo.co.in

Prof. Arvind S. Patel

Professor & Head, Department of Civil Engineering, Faculty of Technology & Engineering, The Maharaja Sayajirao University of Baroda, Vadodara – 390 001.

Email: aspatel_ced@msubaroda.ac.in

ABSTRACT

In recent years, the increasing threat to groundwater quality due to human activities has become a matter of great concern. A vast majority of groundwater quality problems present today are caused by contamination and by over-exploitation, or by combination of both. Rapid urbanization and industrialization in India has resulted in steep increase of generation of wastes. Due to lack of adequate infrastructure and resources the waste is not properly collected, treated and disposed; leading to accumulation and infiltration causing groundwater contamination. The problem is more severe in and around large cities as also various clusters of industries. In many of these areas groundwater is only source of drinking water, thus a large population is exposed to risk of consuming contaminated water. Vadodara, the third populous city of Gujarat and having large industrial potential is has a highly complicated hydro geological condition. The areas have great variations in aquifer thickness as well as the chemical properties of ground water. Along with the surface water ground water plays an important role to be supplied as a source of water for the Vadodara city. It is therefore very important to study the quantity and quality of ground water condition of the City. The study of hydro geological condition is very important as far as the exploration and recharge of ground water is concerned. Through this paper it is attempted to divide the Vadodara city into various zones as per the geo hydrological conditions.

INTRODUCTION :

Ground water is an essential and vital component of our life support system. The ground water resources are being utilized for drinking, irrigation and industrial purposes. However, due to rapid growth of population, urbanization, industrialization and agriculture activities, ground water resources are under stress. There is growing concern on the deterioration of ground water quality due to geogenic and anthropogenic activities.

The natural chemical composition of ground water is influenced predominantly by type & depth of soils and subsurface geological formations through which ground water passes. Ground water quality is also influenced by contribution from the atmosphere and surface water bodies. Quality of ground water is also influenced by anthropogenic factors. For example, overexploitation of ground water in coastal regions may result in sea water ingress and consequent increase in salinity of ground water and excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides in agriculture and improper disposal of urban/industrial waste can cause contamination of ground water resources. Ground water contains a wide variety of dissolved inorganic chemical constituents in various concentrations, resulting from chemical

and biochemical interactions between water and the geological materials. Inorganic contaminants including salinity, chloride, fluoride, nitrate, iron and arsenic are important in determining the suitability of ground water for drinking purposes.

Vadodara, located in the 22° 18' 00" N and 73° 12' 01" E, is one of the famous cities in the central part of the state of Gujarat in India. Situated on the banks of the Vishwamitri river, Vadodara is the fertile plain land between the rivers Narmada and Mahi. As per Census 2011, Vadodara is the third populous city of Gujarat with a total population of 1, 839, 428. Vadodara's weather is dry in nature. The climate of Vadodara is hot between the months of March and July. The maximum temperature of the city during these months is 43°C The minimum temperature in Vadodara is in the month of November to February which is 10°C . The climate in Vadodara becomes humid during the monsoon season. From mid-June to mid-September, the city experiences monsoon season. The average rainfall of Vadodara is recorded as 100 cm. Vadodara weather is also characterized by infrequent torrential rainfall that causes flood in the city. The heavy rainfall between June and September causes the river Vishwamitri, as well as the other rivers of Vadodara to flood.

Sources and Quantity of Water Supply in the City

The main sources of water for the Vadodara city are the Sayaji Sarovar (Ajwa) on the northeast and Mahi river on the northwest of the city. On an average, VMC draws 45-50 MLD from Sayaji Sarovar. The present raw water delivery system is capable of transmitting 45-50 MLD of discharge by gravity to the Nimeta water treatment plant (WTP). The average per capita water supply is around 183 lpcd with a daily supply for 45 minutes twice a day. Tube wells are an alternate source of water supply in VMC. The water from these tube wells is directly injected into the distribution system. Depending upon the area served, the tube wells work from 1 to 18 hours everyday. Based on the capacity of pumps and working hours, the water supplied is believed to be 10 MLD from about 46 tube wells. These well operate in the areas where the water could not be supplied due to pressure problems. Due to the low drawl from these tube wells, the water table in the city does not get impacted. The average water table in the city is around 20 metres and gets recharged regularly due to the presence of perennial rivers in the north. Besides these tube wells, a series of 56 tube wells in the riverbed and around the banks of Mahi have been under development. In all, about 56 tube wells have been sunk. Of these, about 40 wells located on the bank are in working condition with submersible/turbine pumps already installed and commissioned. These tube wells are used in case of shortage of surface water. With the help of these wells, VMC has been tiding over the current water crisis in the last couple of years especially during draught situations.

The city of Vadodara gets its water supply from various sources. The details of the sources of water supply for the city and the approximate quantities from them have been given in Table 1.

Table 1 Sources of water supply

Source Of Supply	Approximate Supply
Mahi Radial Collector Wells	100-120 MLD
Mahi River Tube Wells	55-65 MLD
Ajwa Mimeta	65-70 MLD
City Tube Wells	10-15 Mld
Total Supply	240-270 MLD

Objectives

Following are the objectives of the research work carried out in the paper

1. To divide the Vadodara city into various zones as per quality of the ground water
2. To prepare guide map for Vadodara city for Ground water exploration and Recharge.

Methodology Adopted

The methodology adopted for the study is as follows:

1. Collection of datas regarding quality of ground water in the area.
2. Analysis of data
3. Preparation of graphs showing quality of ground water of the city.

Data Collected

The basic data about the study area was collected from various offices. The data regarding quality of ground water were collected from GWRDC, State Water Data Centre, Public Health Laboratory, VMSS, Vadodara, GWSSB, Vadodara & also from various private water testing laboratories.

ANALYSIS :

The detailed analysis of the quality of ground water for the various areas of the Vadodara city has been shown in Fig.2 to Fig.10. The graphs shows the various parameters for the quality of ground water in the city.

Fig.2 TDS Content in the various areas of the city

Fig.3 pH in the various areas of the city

Fig.4 Total Hardness in the various areas of the city

Fig.8 Sulphate content in the various areas of the city

Fig.5 Calcium content in the various areas of the city

Fig.9 Nitrate content in the various areas of the city

Fig.6 Magnesium content in various areas of the city

Fig.10 Fluoride content in various areas of the city

Fig.7 Chloride content in the various areas of the city

CONCLUSION :

The study of geo hydrological condition is very important as far as the exploration and recharge of the ground water is concerned. The study needs special attention to the city like Vadodara which is highly complicated. Some of the areas are having good aquifers which is good for exploration and recharge, but some of the areas are having non productive saline aquifers which is not good for exploration as well as recharge.

Geohydrology it is recent to sub recent alluvium formation comprises of alluvium Sand, clay, silt, gravel etc) with alternate clay, sand, silt gravel etc. The areas has great variations in aquifer thickness. From the geohydrological point of view, the city can be divided in to different zones depending upon the feasible depth of exploration and possibilities for creation of recharge structures in the area. Table 2 shows the various geo-hydrological zones of Vadodara city. The same have also been shown in Figure 11.

Table 2 Geo-hydrological zones of Vadodara city

Sr No	Area	Zone
1	Alkapuri, Gotri, Sevasi	I
2	Old padara Road, Akota, Atladara	II
3	Manjalpur, Makarpura, Pratnagar	III
4	Ajwa Road, Waghodia Road, Dabhoi Road, Warshia Ring Road, Harni Karelibaug, Harni Road.	IV
5	Subhanpura, Gorwa, IPCL, Refinery area	V
6	Fatehgunj, Nizampura, Sama, Savli Road, Chhani road	VI
7	City, Mandvi, Nyaymandir, Wadi, Fatehpura, Raopura, Panigate.	Mix

The Bureau of Indian Standards (BIS) earlier known as Indian Standards Institution (ISI) has laid down the standard specifications for drinking water (BIS, 1991). In order to enable the users, exercise their discretion towards water quality criteria, the maximum permissible limit has been prescribed especially where no alternate source is available. The national water quality standards describe essential and desirable characteristics required to be evaluated to assess suitability of water for drinking purpose (Table 3)

Table 3 Drinking water specifications (IS:10500:1991)

Parameter	Desirable Limit	Permissible Limit	Area Having more value than permissible
TDS	500	2000	Dabhoi Road, Dandia Bazar, Kapurai, Waghodia Road
pH	6.5-8.5	6.5-8.5	-----
Total Hardness	300	600	Dandia Bazar, Waghodia Road
Calcium	75	200	-----
Magnesium	30	75	Alkapuri, Dandia Bazar, Kapurai,

Parameter	Desirable Limit	Permissible Limit	Area Having more value than permissible
Chloride	250	1000	Makarpura, Maneja, Waghodia Road
Sulphate	200	400	Kapurai
Nitrate	45	100	-----
Fluoride	1.0	1.5	Diwalipura, Waghodia Road, Tarsali.

From the above table, it is cleared that Zone I,II,III,V and VI has a moderate quality of ground water. Zone V has a saline aquifer which is not good for exploration as well as recharge.

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Figure 11 Geo hydrological Zones of Vadodara City